

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2004–2005

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, had advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

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(AS OF JUNE 30, 2005)

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KATHLIN SMITH
Director of Communications

LETTER FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Charles Phelps
Chairman of the Board

A CLIR VIEW OF THE FUTURE

I hope that you will forgive the pun in the title of this piece—puns are a personal addiction—but I wanted to focus attention both on the vision that CLIR has formulated for itself and on the processes that led to the articulation of that vision.

First, a word on process. Throughout the years, CLIR has been fortunate to have a highly capable and diverse Board, representing the worlds of academia, libraries, and publishing. Our Board has also been diverse geographically, with representation from countries beyond U.S. borders. The current Board, particularly through the Executive Committee, has served as a resource for strategic planning. Members have participated not only in regular Board meetings but also in special-purpose meetings, including a retreat in June 2005 that helped shape CLIR's strategic focus for the future. Building on the Board's discussions, the CLIR staff subsequently developed a strategic plan, which was embedded in a proposal for core support that CLIR submitted to, and which was recently funded by, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

The vision for CLIR, and our plan for realizing that vision, are tremendously exciting. CLIR helps people think about and shape the future of the world of libraries. For example, *Library as Place: Rethinking Roles, Rethinking Space*, a report that CLIR published early this year, informed the Board's discussions of libraries as something other than document repositories. Perhaps because of my fondness for wordplay, I was especially pleased with the part of the strategic plan that we now call "the place as library." This phrase reflects the consequences of making available in digital form material once accessible only within the library's walls. Increasingly, libraries are organizations that gather information about where to find things, rather than entities that have such things in their own collections. Thus, an entire college or university, or a consortium of such institutions, can become extensions of the library. This concept, and other elements of CLIR's new strategic focus—scholarly communication, preservation and stewardship, and leadership—will help shape our work as we move forward.

As I look forward to our future, I want to thank all those who, during the past 50 years, have helped make CLIR a powerful force for thinking about the future. The list of people to whom we are indebted is considerable. It

includes former and current staff members and consultants, former and current members of the Board, members of various CLIR advisory groups, and the people and organizations that have provided the funds that enable CLIR to continue its work. As we approach an important milestone in CLIR's history and look forward to the future, it seems appropriate to reflect on and acknowledge the contributions of those who have helped us in the past.

Charles E. Phelps

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Nancy A. Davenport
President

It's late August as I write this message, and my thoughts keep straying to the tragedy in New Orleans. Like Americans across the country, I've been horrified by the newspaper headlines and moved by the images in print and on television. At the same time, e-mails from librarians pop up on my computer, reminding us to donate to the Red Cross and other relief organizations and asking whether we have spare room to take in displaced librarians. And, even at this early stage, these librarians have been raising the questions of how to set about to recover damaged collections—provided that there are indeed collections to save.

Libraries have had visible roles in the hurricane aftermath. I've been struck by how many photos show people being rescued from public libraries and, conversely, the number of libraries in safe places that have invited the evacuees to come and use their computers to find shelter, family, jobs, and even distraction from their daily woes. The number of public libraries that have taken bookmobiles and story hours to shelters is both impressive and heartening.

Thus, while the tragedy reminds us of our fragility, it also underscores the strong, pervasive role that music, art, dance, performance, libraries, and museums hold in our lives. They are an integral part of our culture. The City of New Orleans is known around the globe for its unique culture: The possibility that it could not be restored is profoundly unsettling, if not unimaginable. At CLIR, we have seen this tragedy as a reaffirmation of the need for our mission—the preservation of and access to recorded knowledge.

My first year as CLIR's president has been exhilarating. I've traveled extensively to meet our sponsors. I've talked with them about goals for CLIR and learned more about why they see a need for an organization such as ours. My colleague Abby Smith often says, "The role of CLIR is to see issues from 30,000 feet—to think strategically for the libraries and scholars too swamped with the day-to-day details of myriad issues to do so themselves." We continue to do that thinking every day.

This report provides details on CLIR's activities and accomplishments of the past year. I'd like to highlight just a few of them here. As libraries add digital resources to augment their resources and as students increasingly rely on Internet resources, predictions abound about the imminent death

of libraries. CLIR's report *Library as Place: Rethinking Roles, Rethinking Space*, issued in February 2005, recasts libraries as the hubs of the learning space on campus—as the ideal places for collaborative learning. This report was pivotal in helping CLIR's Board and staff rethink our programmatic focus for the next three years. It also served as a foundation document for an invitational symposium that we cosponsored with American University as it began to think about how to recast the library and its services for future generations of students.

CLIR sponsored the sixth, and very lively, Frye Institute with our partners Educause and Emory University. Brian Hawkins, president of Educause; Susan Perry, director of programs at CLIR; and I served as deans for this year's institute. Plans are already under way for the June 2006 program, and application materials are available on our Web site for this important leadership program.

With the Digital Library Federation, in February we sponsored a seminar for liberal arts colleges on managing digital assets. The College of Charleston was our host institution, and participants toured the new library expressing admiration at every stop.

For several years, CLIR has facilitated a set of meetings for the chief information officers (CIOs) of a group of academic institutions that have blended their library and academic information technology operations. The CLIR CIOs, as they are known, sponsored a conference in March 2005 at Kenyon College for the directors of these merged departments and those who report to them. This event was a conference planner's dream. Participants abandoned the printed agenda to focus on important issues of common concern.

At our April Sponsors' Symposium, "Transforming Libraries," provosts, academic officers, and a publisher gave their perspectives on scholarly communication issues. The speakers were peppered with questions from the audience about how changes in the creation, distribution, and preservation of scholarly work have involved the library. CLIR will celebrate its 50th anniversary in 2006, as the successor organization to the merged Council on Library Resources and the Commission on Preservation and Access. We will celebrate that past at our Sponsors' Symposium next April.

CLIR took steps this year to become more directly involved in issues of public policy that affect libraries and the scholarly community. CLIR was appointed to the U.S. National Commission for UNESCO as the only nongovernmental organization from the information and scholarly sector. There are multiple conventions and treaties under negotiation that would

affect the scholarly world, especially in the intellectual property sphere. And late in the year, I was elected to the Board of Directors of the National Information Standards Organization, a vitally important body in our increasingly networked environment.

As many readers of this report already know, the Digital Library Federation (DLF) became a separate, not-for-profit corporation this spring. The DLF will continue to be a program of CLIR, and CLIR will provide staff and administrative services to the DLF. Whereas we previously operated seamlessly on the basis of a handshake, we now operate seamlessly under a contract for services. To reinforce ties between the two organizations, the CLIR Board has offered a seat on its Board to a representative of the DLF.

It has been a pleasure to work with the CLIR Board and most especially with the Executive Committee as we developed a new, three-year agenda for CLIR. We have decided that our research and programs will focus on four areas: place as library, scholarly communication, preservation and stewardship, and leadership development. More details and a fuller discussion of each area will be published in *CLIR Issues*. In addition, the Board has elected six new members, each of whom will begin service at our fall 2005 meeting. They are Charles Brown, director of Charlotte-Mecklenburg County Public Library; Mark Dimunation, chief of Rare Books and Special Collections at the Library of Congress; Wendy Lougee, university librarian at the University of Minnesota; Claudia Lux, director of the Berlin Municipal Library and president elect of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions; Stephen Nichols, professor of French and humanities at the Johns Hopkins University; and Georgia Nugent, president of Kenyon College.

As any organization, large or small, does, CLIR experienced staff turnover during the past year. Program Associate Cynthia Burns left in April to continue her graduate studies in counseling. Program Director Abby Smith left CLIR in July, although she continues to work with us as a contractor. We welcomed Gary Romero as our administrative associate. I express to the staff my gratitude for their support during this first year as well as my admiration for their outstanding work.

Finally, on behalf of the entire organization, I would like to express thanks for the generosity of our sponsors, donors, and other funders. We are grateful for the support that you give both financially and intellectually as we develop new programs to respond to emerging issues.

Nancy Davenport

THE PROGRAMS

RESOURCES FOR SCHOLARSHIP

2005 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Kevin Bartig, Musicology, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Ellen Boucher, History, Columbia University

Vanesa Casanova-Fernandez, History-Middle East, Georgetown University

Zeynep Celik bei Opitz, Architectural History, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Hallie Franks, Art History / Architectural History, Harvard University

Carolina Giraldo Botero, History, Rutgers, The State University of New Jersey

Sarah Hamill, Art History, University of California, Berkeley

Erin Hasinoff, Anthropology, Columbia University

Laura Anne Kalba, History-Modern Europe, University of Southern California

Loretta Kim, History, Harvard University

Andrew Manson, Art History-Archaeology-Architecture, Columbia University

Maximilian Owre, History, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Dassia N. Posner, Theater, Tufts University

Lindsay Weiss, Archaeology-Anthropology, Columbia University

Susie Woo, History-American Studies, Yale University

Scholarly Communication Institute

The Scholarly Communication Institute (SCI) was established in 2003 to provide an opportunity for leaders in the field of scholarly communication to study, plan, and organize institutional and discipline-based strategies for advancing the state of scholarly communication. The second SCI, held in July 2004 at the University of Virginia (UVa), focused on practical ethics, an interdisciplinary field noted for its history of working in collaborative modes, of being open to change, and of being friendly to pragmatism in the service of scholarship. SCI2 drew teams of scholars, graduate students, librarians, academic officers, and technologists from four institutions: the Kenan Institute for Ethics at Duke University; the Poynter Center for the Study of Ethics and American Institutions at Indiana University; the Center for Bioethics at the University of Minnesota; and the Institute for Practical Ethics and Public Life at UVa. The teams left the institute with plans to model and test an idea for a common information resource—specifically, a repository for case studies that will be populated with cases from different fields.

ACLS Cyberinfrastructure Commission

The word *cyberinfrastructure* describes new research environments in which sophisticated computing tools are available to researchers across all disciplines by means of an interoperable network. In 2004, with support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the American Council of Learned Societies (ACLS) formed a commission to investigate and report on the development of a cyberinfrastructure for the humanities and social sciences. The commission held six public information-gathering sessions in 2004 and concluded its investigations early in 2005. Its report will address the potential role of cyberinfrastructure in advancing the humanities and social sciences and will describe how these domains, in turn, can contribute to the emerging cyberinfrastructure. CLIR Program Director Abby Smith served as editor of the commission's report, which will be circulated for public comment late in 2005.

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships for Research in Original Sources

The Mellon Dissertation Fellowship program supports original-source doctoral research in libraries and archives, without regard to the location or the format of those sources. In 2005, 15 fellows were selected from more than 350 candidates. As in years past, the fellows proposed work in a wide range of repositories, and their topics of study were similarly broad in scope. In May, the fellows convened at the Library of Congress (LC) for a one-day workshop on research in archives and special collections.

PRESERVATION AWARENESS

National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program

CLIR continues to provide expertise, technical support, and other services to help the Library of Congress (LC) coordinate the work of the National Digital Information Infrastructure and Preservation Program (NDIIPP). The NDIIPP legislation, passed in December 2000, called for a phased approach to building an infrastructure of cooperating institutions to achieve a decentralized yet coherent response to the challenge of long-term preservation of digital content.

In 2004, CLIR staff oversaw two of the eight preservation partnerships that were inaugurated late in the year, advised NDIIPP on its digital collection activities, and headed an investigation that is beginning to track the economics of archiving. Staff members also provided meeting support and other administrative assistance as requested by LC.

A separate set of tasks, all addressing the preservation of recorded sound in the national digital preservation network, proceeded through the year. CLIR commissioned several technical reports on recorded-sound engineering and copyright that will be published in late 2005 and 2006.

DIGITAL LIBRARIES

Managing Digital Assets Workshop

In February 2005, CLIR and the Digital Library Federation offered a three-day workshop for library and information technology administrators seeking in-depth information about the planning, purchase, implementation, and management of digital assets. The workshop, “Managing Digital Assets,” focused on trends in digital content management and on how small and midsize academic libraries can incorporate new approaches into their operations. The session offered library and information managers tools with which to evaluate the alternatives now available and to begin to chart digital asset management strategies for their institutions.

A second workshop, aimed at research libraries and cosponsored with the Association of Research Libraries, will be held in fall 2005.

Transforming Libraries

CLIR held its annual Sponsors' Symposium, "Transforming Libraries," in April 2005. The symposium's topic was inspired by Google's agreement with five research libraries to digitize millions of holdings in their collections. The symposium's seven panelists explored the implications of this development—and others that will contribute to universal access—for academic institutions, libraries, and publishers.

Digital Library Federation

The Digital Library Federation (DLF) is a consortium of 34 members and 5 allied organizations that are pioneering the use of electronic information technologies to extend library collections and services. In 2004–2005, DLF gained a new member, Egypt's Bibliotheca Alexandrina, and a new ally, the Joint Information Systems Committee of the Higher and Further Education Council (JISC), a United Kingdom–based funding agency. In May 2005, DLF incorporated.

Highlights of DLF work in 2004–2005 include the following.

DLF Aquifer. DLF continued work to develop a distributed, open library of digitized holdings as a basis on which to build tools and services that promote better scholarship and teaching. In January 2005, Katherine Kott of Stanford University was appointed full-time director of DLF Aquifer. Under her coordination, working committees in collections, metadata, technical architecture, and services have been shaping a prototype service, using American cultural materials already digitized in our libraries, to improve discovery and reuse of collections that are currently scattered and not integrated.

Sharable metadata. A key challenge to the distributed library is refining best practices for the creation of sharable, interoperable metadata—catalog records for digital objects that can be exposed to software that travels the Web, harvests records from many sites, brings them back to a central point, and aggregates them, thereby making it possible to provide discovery services to hundreds of sites from a single Web service point. The metadata gathered by this method is precise and can provide access to the "dark Web," that is, publicly available library and museum content missed by search engines such as Google and Yahoo! In October 2004, with the support of a \$292,000 national leadership grant from the Institute of Museum and Library Services (IMLS), DLF gathered experts in the field of harvestable metadata and charged them with developing best-practices guidelines on how to build harvestable records en masse that work easily in an interoperable manner. The guidelines are now in draft form.

This work builds on past DLF investments in the development of the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH). It includes a prototype single portal for digital library objects with OAI records, addressing users' complaints that resource discovery takes too long and that tools such as Google or the OPAC miss too much material.

Responding to scholars' needs. In 2004, DLF convened a group of scholars working on digital projects, editions, and archives as a planning and a reaction panel for DLF activities. In June 2005, as part of its IMLS-funded work, DLF convened a similar group; this time, however, the discussions focused on the scholarly potential of services that use OAI-harvestable metadata. This type of formal feedback continues to pay dividends, as the scholars made significant contributions to the design of the OAI-based DLF portal. For example, scholars emphasized that users often want to be able to download the metadata for a book, slide, or manuscript that they have found in a digital library in order to build personal research libraries or bibliographies of citations to online material.

Preservation-quality digital images. In June 2004, the U.S. National Archives and Records Administration (NARA) Digital Imaging Lab issued technical guidelines for creating digital surrogates of still images to facilitate access and reproduction. The guidelines state that they are *not* intended to apply to preservation formatting—that is, the creation of surrogates that will replace original records. In April 2005, DLF convened a team from NARA, LC, Kodak, the Swiss Institute of Technology, Harvard University, and elsewhere and commissioned it to build on the NARA report to produce a statement of the best that is collectively now known about preservation-quality digital images and the information about them that should be recorded for the long term.

Electronic Resources Management Initiative (ERMI). ERMI has created and disseminated a common, sharable, XML database record for expressing the content of license agreements, related administrative information, and internal processes associated with collections of licensed electronic resources. Use of the record saves libraries the time-consuming effort of retyping publishers' diverse license terms into their management systems.

Publishers are now willing to deliver their licenses to libraries in a common XML record format, and vendors are providing software that makes it simple to load these records into library management systems. In fall 2005, DLF will cosponsor with the National Information Standards Organizations and EDItEUR the next round of implementation and real-world formalization and testing to move libraries to a more-efficient license-expression workflow.

Interoperation of learning management and library information systems.

Learning management systems are ubiquitous in higher education, and the number of Internet-accessible collections of digital resources relevant to teachers and students is growing rapidly. As these sites are increasingly produced through formal learning management systems, it is important to consider how such systems interact with external repositories and discovery systems. In 2003–2004, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation funded a DLF study group to examine the interaction of digital libraries and learning management, or courseware, systems. DLF issued a report of the group's findings, titled *Digital Library Content and Course Management Systems: Issues of Interoperation*, in July 2004.

DLF Forum. The DLF semiannual forums—in Baltimore last fall and in San Diego this spring—each drew about 200 attendees. The Forum Fellowships for Librarians New to the Profession continue to attract new library staff to the forums, exposing them to a range of issues and providing opportunities to make new contacts. Fellowship recipients this year came from the University of Minnesota, Cornell University, Emory University, North Carolina State University, The Johns Hopkins University, the University of Tennessee, Dartmouth College, and the California Digital Library.

LEADERSHIP

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Scholarly Information Resources in the Humanities

The CLIR postdoctoral fellowship program, offered in conjunction with a consortium of academic research institutions, seeks to create a new kind of scholarly information professional—one who believes that there are opportunities to develop meaningful linkages among disciplinary scholarship, libraries, archives, and evolving digital tools. The fellowships are open to individuals who have recently completed their Ph.D. degrees in a humanities discipline.

CLIR awarded four fellowships, each of one to two years in length, for 2005–2006. Participating schools are Bryn Mawr College; the University of California, Berkeley; the University of California, Los Angeles; the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; and the University of Virginia. Participants began their fellowships with a two-week preparatory seminar at Bryn Mawr College in Pennsylvania and in Washington, D.C. Throughout their fellowships, participants will “meet” monthly in a virtual classroom, developed by the University of Illinois Graduate School of Library and Information Science, for lectures and discussions.

2005–2006 Fellows in Scholarly Information Resources

<i>Fellow</i>	<i>Fellowship Host Institution</i>
Marlene Allen	UCLA
Ali Anooshahr	UCLA
Kelly Miller	University of Virginia
Michelle Morton	University of California, Berkeley

Frye Institute Participants Class of 2005

Kenning Arlitsch, University of Utah
Charles Bartel, Carnegie Mellon University
Sharon Blanton, Scottsdale Community College
Andrew Bonamici, University of Oregon
Scott Britton, Washington University Libraries
Debra Bruxvoort, Central College
W. Gardner Campbell, University of Mary Washington
Beth Chancellor, University of Missouri-Columbia
Helen Chu, California Polytechnic State Univ., San Luis Obispo
Robert Clougherty, Jr., Tennessee Technological University
Sylvia Contreras, Edgewood College
Lorie Edwards, University of South Carolina
John Fritz, University of Maryland, Baltimore Cty.
Chandra Gigliotti-Guridi, Hampden-Sydney College
Chris Gill, Gonzaga University
Al Gonzalez, Cornell University
Lynn Gunn, Marquette University
Richard Holmgren, Allegheny College
Judith House, Georgetown University
Jim Jorstad, University of Wisconsin-LaCrosse
Dawn Kight, Southern University and A & M College
Barron Koralesky, Macalester College
David Levin, California State Polytechnic University, Pomona
Julie Little, University of Tennessee
William Mayer, The George Washington University
Jenny Mehmedovic, University of Kansas
Mary Parlett-Sweeney, Union College
Medaline Philbert, Pace University
Faye Priestly, Johnson C. Smith University
Ulrich Rauch, University of British Columbia
Michael Reder, Connecticut College
Jane Schillie, University of Miami
Tracy Schroeder, University of San Francisco
Sonya Shepherd, Georgia Southern University
Dale Smith, University of Oregon
Sarah Stein, North Carolina State University
Betsy Tippens, University of Washington, Bothell
Timothy Tolson, University of Virginia
Andrew Treloar, Monash University
Jeffrey Trzeciak, Wayne State University
Joseph Vaughan, UCLA
Richard Wake, University of Southampton
Carolyn Walters, Indiana University, Bloomington
Jennifer Ward, University of Washington Libraries
John Williams, University of Michigan

Frye Leadership Institute

The Frye Leadership Institute was created to develop leaders who can guide and transform academic information services for higher education. Since its inception in 2000, the institute has trained nearly 300 librarians, faculty members, and technology experts. The 2005 institute was held June 5–17 at the Emory Conference Center in Atlanta, Georgia. The class of 45 participants came from public and private institutions of all sizes, and included one representative each from Canada, Great Britain, and Australia. Nancy Davenport, Brian Hawkins, and Susan Perry served as deans of the Institute, which is supported with funds from The Robert W. Woodruff Foundation.

Chief Information Officers of Liberal Arts Colleges

CLIR's Chief Information Officers (CIO) Group is composed of 34 directors of organizations that have merged their library and information technology (IT) units on the campuses of liberal arts colleges and small universities. The group met at Kenyon College in March 2005 for a symposium to which directors of such blended units and staff who report directly to them were invited. Participants explored issues such as whether a merged organization can provide better service to students and faculty than a traditional organization can. To evaluate the services that merged information organizations are providing, the CIO Group endorsed a project to survey users on several campuses. Survey results will allow a college to benchmark its services against those of other schools.

Early in 2005, two members of the group, Bob Johnson of Rhodes College and Terry Metz of Wheaton College, edited an issue of *Transformations*, an online journal sponsored by the Associated Colleges of the South. The theme of the issue was the merging of information services organizations, combining IT and library functions in a single organizational structure, and the effects of such mergers on expectations, spaces, functions, and language. Several members of the CIO group contributed to the issue.

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

The Academic Librarians Advisory Committee advises CLIR on issues of interest to liberal arts colleges and small research libraries. In February 2005, the committee sponsored a workshop, "Managing Digital Assets" (see page 7). The committee continues to work on ways of ensuring that senior staff in their institutions understand the needs and contributions of their libraries in a changing information environment.

A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management

Richard Swart was named the recipient of the 2005 A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management. A Ph.D. student in business information systems and education at Utah State University, Mr. Swart is the ninth

recipient of the fellowship, which was established in 1997 to recognize a graduate student who shows exceptional promise for leadership and technical achievement in information management. Mr. Swart's research areas include semantic integration, management and security of widely distributed and Web services-enabled data stores, and handling threats from those seeking to disrupt or intercept information flow.

INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENTS

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Access to Learning Award

Bangladesh's Shidhulai Swanirvar Sangstha received the 2005 Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Access to Learning Award. The nongovernmental organization was recognized for its use of indigenous boats converted into mobile libraries, schools, and educational units that employ generators or solar energy and mobile phones for Internet access. The boats travel to rural communities in a northern Bangladesh watershed, even during monsoon season, to educate women, men, and children on issues ranging from agricultural practices to microenterprise and health concerns.

The annual award, which totals US \$1 million, recognizes innovative efforts of libraries or similar kinds of organizations outside the United States in providing no-cost public access to computer technology, particularly in underserved communities. Past recipients include libraries and organizations in Argentina, China, Colombia, Denmark, Finland, Guatemala, and South Africa. This is the fourth year that CLIR has managed the award.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Alison Raab, a graduate student in the School of Information and Library Science at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, was named the third recipient of the Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship. Ms. Raab has an M.A. degree in Japanese history from the University of California, Davis, and lived and worked in Japan for six years. The award, which CLIR administers with funding provided by Mathilde and Howard Rovelstad, provides travel funds for a student of library and information science to attend the World Library and Information Congress.

PUBLICATIONS

JULY 1, 2004–JUNE 30, 2005

MONOGRAPHS AND REPORTS

Library as Place: Rethinking Roles, Rethinking Space. February 2005. Available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub129abst.html>.

Survey of the State of Audio Collections in Academic Libraries. Abby Smith, David Randal Allen, and Karen Allen. August 2004. Available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub128abst.html>.

NEWSLETTERS

CLIR Issues, nos. 40-45. Available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/issues/index.html>.

ADVISORY GROUPS

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Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

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Stephen Melville
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Sarah Porter
Joint Information Systems Committee

Alice Prochaska
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H. Carton Rogers
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Gloriana St. Clair
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David M. Seaman (*ex officio*)
Digital Library Federation

Ismail Serageldin
Bibliotheca Alexandrina

Winston Tabb
Johns Hopkins University

Kenneth Thibodeau
National Archives and Records
Administration

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Cornell University

Suzanne Thorin
Indiana University

Karin A. Trainer
Princeton University

Lizabeth Wilson
University of Washington

Karin Wittenborg
University of Virginia

Ann Wolpert
Massachusetts Institute of Technology

* indicates DLF Allies

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN FY 2005

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Appalachian College Association Jefferson City, TN	To support a work redesign project for the Appalachian College Association libraries	11/11/2003	\$100,000
Atlanta University Center Atlanta, GA	To support a work redesign project for the Woodruff Library at the Atlanta University Center	10/15/2003	\$100,000
Besek, June New York, NY	To conduct a study of copyright issues implicated by the preservation of digital works by libraries and archives	1/21/2005	\$12,000
Brogan, Martha New Haven, CT	To revise for general publication the internal report <i>Surveying the Landscape of Digital American Literature</i>	1/26/2005	\$19,400
Brooks, Tim Greenwich, CT	To design and report the results of a study for LC and the National Recording Preservation Board	6/16/2004	\$5,000
Bryn Mawr College Bryn Mawr, PA	To hold a two-week intensive workshop for CLIR's Post-Doctoral Fellowship recipients	5/12/2004	\$10,725
Columbia University New York, NY	To write two analyses of copyright with respect to recorded sound	6/2/2004	\$17,000
Emory University Atlanta, GA	To facilitate Emory University's collaborative effort in the project: "The DLF Distributed Library: OAI for Digital Library Aggregation"	10/1/2004	\$40,684
Five Colleges of Ohio, Inc. Gambier, OH	To support a work redesign project for the Five Colleges of Ohio, Inc. libraries	11/11/2003	\$100,000
IFLA The Hague, Netherlands	To support the IFLA Core Programme for Preservation and Conservation	4/15/2002	\$20,000
IPSolutions, Inc. San Mateo, CA	To assemble and coordinate management consultant services for NDSAB and NDIIPP	5/25/2005	\$306,275
Jackson, Jack Arhus, Denmark	To write a case study of the Aarhus Public Libraries in Denmark	11/22/2004	\$18,500
Kingsbury, Paul Nashville, TN	To write a summary report of a meeting of audio engineers convened on behalf of the Library of Congress and the National Recording Preservation Board	12/29/2003	\$3,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
The Libraries of The Claremont Colleges Claremont, CA	To support a work redesign project for The Libraries of The Claremont Colleges	1/20/2004	\$88,400
Liu, Geoffrey Z. Mountain View, CA	To write a case study in English and Chinese of the China Evergreen Rural Library Service in China	11/22/2004	\$10,546
Oliver, Kate Baltimore, MD	To write an essay on new services at the Welch Library	6/15/2004	\$1,500
Shanghai Library Shanghai, China	To partially support the Third China/U.S. Conference on Libraries	7/23/2004	\$5,000
Shirky, Clay Brooklyn, NY	To support NDIIPP work to define and implement a technical architecture	5/25/2005	\$50,000
Shore, Elliott Wynnewood, PA	To direct the CLIR Post-Doctoral Fellowship for 2004–2005	5/12/2004	\$15,000
Silha, Stephen Vashon Island, WA	To research and write an evaluation of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Access to Learning Award	5/11/2004	\$16,600
Smith College Libraries Northampton, MA	To support a work redesign project for the Smith College Libraries	1/20/2004	\$100,000
Smolian Sound Studios Frederick, MD	To implement and contribute to reporting the results of a study for LC and National Recording Preservation Board	6/30/2004	\$11,000
Tri-College Consortium Libraries Haverford, PA	To support a work redesign project for the Tri-College Consortium Libraries	1/20/2004	\$100,000
Troll Covey, Denise Pittsburgh, PA	To write a report on negotiating copyright for digitizing projects	2/28/2005	\$2,500
University of Illinois Champaign, IL	To facilitate the University of Illinois' effort in the project: "The DLF Distributed Library: OAI for Digital Library Aggregation"	10/1/2004	\$66,377
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI	To facilitate the University of Michigan's effort in the project: "The DLF Distributed Library: OAI for Digital Library Aggregation"	10/1/2004	\$225,957
University of Virginia Library Charlottesville, VA	To support the 2004 Scholarly Communication Institute	1/14/2004	\$85,146
University of Virginia Library Charlottesville, VA	To provide administrative support for the 2005 Scholarly Communication Institute	6/1/2005	\$75,000

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2005
(With Summarized Financial Information for June 30, 2004)

WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
 Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Trustees
 Council on Library and Information Resources
 Washington, D.C.

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2005, and the related statements of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit. The prior year summarized comparative information has been derived from the organization's 2004 financial statements and, in our report dated August 26, 2004 we expressed an unqualified opinion on those financial statements.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2005, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The accompanying schedule of functional expenses is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
 August 15, 2005

Members American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2005

(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2004)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2005</u>	<u>Total 2004</u>
Assets				
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 339,392	\$ 1,853,003	\$ 2,192,395	\$ 892,328
Investments	400,000	5,347,980	5,747,980	6,985,390
Accounts receivable	196,028	429,700	625,728	437,406
Furniture and equipment, net	40,420	-	40,420	37,974
Other assets	<u>27,074</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>27,074</u>	<u>28,920</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 1,002,914</u>	<u>\$ 7,630,683</u>	<u>\$ 8,633,597</u>	<u>\$ 8,382,018</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets				
Accounts payable	\$ 287,020	\$ -	\$ 287,020	\$ 587,227
Accrued expenses	51,897	-	51,897	55,935
Sublet deposits	<u>3,859</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>3,859</u>	<u>2,956</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 342,776</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 342,776</u>	<u>\$ 646,118</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 660,138</u>	<u>\$ 7,630,683</u>	<u>\$ 8,290,821</u>	<u>\$ 7,735,900</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,002,914</u>	<u>\$ 7,630,683</u>	<u>\$ 8,633,597</u>	<u>\$ 8,382,018</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2005
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2004)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2005</u>	<u>Total 2004</u>
Revenue				
Grants and contracts	\$ 270,047	\$ 2,278,047	\$ 2,548,094	\$ 4,578,491
Contributions	506,395	2,613,809	3,120,204	2,049,408
Publication sales	13,975	-	13,975	8,589
Investment income	79,224	159,292	238,516	252,683
Other income	<u>93,074</u>	<u>13,650</u>	<u>106,724</u>	<u>6,584</u>
	<u>\$ 962,715</u>	<u>\$ 5,064,798</u>	<u>\$ 6,027,513</u>	<u>\$ 6,895,755</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions				
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 4,534,699</u>	<u>\$ (4,534,699)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 5,497,414</u>	<u>\$ 530,099</u>	<u>\$ 6,027,513</u>	<u>\$ 6,895,755</u>
Expenses				
Program services:				
Preservation	\$ 1,803,668	\$ -	\$ 1,803,668	\$ 2,232,253
Leadership	1,669,674	-	1,669,674	2,456,494
Digital libraries	1,112,385	-	1,112,385	934,448
Resources for scholarship	267,294	-	267,294	322,859
Education	53,769	-	53,769	35,067
Economics of information	<u>3,867</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>3,867</u>	<u>21,835</u>
Total Program services	<u>\$ 4,910,657</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 4,910,657</u>	<u>\$ 6,002,956</u>
Administration	<u>561,935</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>561,935</u>	<u>546,120</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 5,472,592</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 5,472,592</u>	<u>\$ 6,549,076</u>
Change in Net Assets	\$ 24,822	\$ 530,099	\$ 554,921	\$ 346,679
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>\$ 635,316</u>	<u>\$ 7,100,584</u>	<u>\$ 7,735,900</u>	<u>\$ 7,389,221</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 660,138</u>	<u>\$ 7,630,683</u>	<u>\$ 8,290,821</u>	<u>\$ 7,735,900</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2005
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2004)

	<u>2005</u>	<u>2004</u>
Operating Activities		
Change in net assets	\$ 554,921	\$ 346,679
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities		
Depreciation	22,561	24,072
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	(72,856)	(84,269)
Realized (gain)loss on investments	(165,660)	(167,441)
(Increase) decrease in other assets	1,846	2,816
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	(188,322)	18,010
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	(304,245)	246,053
Increase (decrease) in Sublet Deposit	903	
Increase (decrease) in deferred revenue	<u>-</u>	<u>(135,000)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Operating Activities	\$ <u>(150,852)</u>	\$ <u>250,920</u>
Investing Activities		
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 16,880,625	\$ 7,474,375
Purchases of investments	(15,404,700)	(8,487,079)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(25,006)</u>	<u>(21,812)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Investing Activities	\$ <u>1,450,919</u>	\$ <u>(1,034,516)</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ 1,300,067	\$ (783,596)
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>892,328</u>	<u>1,675,924</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	\$ <u><u>2,192,395</u></u>	\$ <u><u>892,328</u></u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information		
Interest paid during the year	\$ -	\$ -

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2005

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council's operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent sponsor fees billings, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council has not recorded any amount for the allowance for doubtful accounts because the Council receives funds on a cost reimbursement basis and sponsors dues are current.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2005
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs which include rent and other expenses are identified as support services costs and have been allocated directly to programs and administration. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2005 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

Summarized financial information - The financial statements include certain prior year comparative information summarized in total but not by net asset class. Such information does not include sufficient detail to constitute a presentation in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles. Accordingly, such information should be read in conjunction with the Council's financial statements for the year ended June 30, 2004 from which the summarized information was derived.

Reclassification of prior year information - Certain amounts from the prior year have been reclassified to enhance comparability.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2005
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Investments – The Organization has adopted SFAS No. 124, “Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations.” Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2005

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ 4,658	\$ (7,785)	\$ 81,763
Corporate fixed income	32,298	(6,413)	1,557,603
Government securities	78,820	4,760	2,641,280
Certificate of deposit	5,014	-	13,922
Mutual funds	<u>33,702</u>	<u>82,294</u>	<u>1,453,412</u>
Subtotal	\$ 154,492	\$ 72,856	\$ <u>5,747,980</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>11,168</u>	-	\$ <u>1,807,610</u>
Total	\$ <u>165,660</u>	\$ <u>72,856</u>	

NOTE 3 - Income Taxes

The Council is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

NOTE 4 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

	<u>2005</u>	<u>2004</u>
Furniture and equipment	\$ 184,466	\$ 177,666
Equipment under capital lease	17,641	-
Leasehold improvements	<u>4,015</u>	<u>4,015</u>
	206,122	181,681
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(165,702)</u>	<u>(143,707)</u>
	\$ <u>40,420</u>	\$ <u>37,974</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2005
(Continued)

NOTE 5 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 6 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council’s defined contribution retirement annuity program (“the Plan”) administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council’s contributions. The Council contributes 15% of employees’ salaries to the Plan each year. The Council’s contributions were \$135,000 and \$173,270 in 2005 and 2004, respectively.

NOTE 7 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2005 and 2004, approximately \$1,807,186 and \$566,716 respectively, in cash equivalents was being held by third parties in money market accounts that invest solely in United States government securities. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2005 and 2004 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$615,332 and \$308,373. Furthermore, all balances in investment accounts are uninsured.

NOTE 8 – Accounts Receivable

	June 30, <u>2005</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 208,463
30 – 60 days	55,813
60 – 90 days	-
Over 90 days	361,452
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	\$ <u><u>625,728</u></u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2005
(Concluded)

NOTE 9 - Commitments

The Council has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August 2008. The Council is subleasing a portion of its space until September 2006, with an option to renew. Rental expense, net of sublease income for the year ending June 30, 2005 was \$178,769. The Council is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in June 1, 2010. Future minimum lease payments under all leases with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending	Capital	Operating
<u>June 30, _____</u>	<u>Lease</u>	<u>Leases</u>
2005	3,588	152,064
2006	3,588	153,896
2007	3,588	117,756
2008	3,588	165,760
2009	<u>8,158</u>	<u>27,805</u>
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 22,510	\$ <u>617,281</u>
Less: Amount representing interest.	<u>(4,869)</u>	
Present value of net minimum lease payments	\$ <u>17,641</u>	

NOTE 10- Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to restrict net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 11- Subsequent Events

The Digital Library Federation has organized into a separate legal entity as of July 1, 2005.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

For the Year Ended June 30, 2005
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2004)

	Digital Libraries	Economics of Information	Leadership	Preservation	Education	Scholarship	Resources For Program Services	Admin.	Total 2005	Total 2004
Grants & Contracts Refunds	\$ 49,500	\$ -	\$ 1,071,963	\$ -	\$ 13,500	\$ 208,800	\$ 1,343,763	\$ 34,501	\$ 1,378,264	\$ 2,201,932 (12,800)
Meeting & Travel	491,200	1,441	260,249	7,238	39,686	24,581	824,395	47,351	871,746	779,621
Project Expenditures	10,158	-	82,391	1,231,309	-	-	1,323,858	-	1,323,858	1,470,166
Communications	9,606	-	314	275	-	-	10,195	12,607	22,802	26,664
Staff	424,945	-	191,814	546,006	-	29,148	1,191,913	80,133	1,272,046	1,594,972
Consultants	19,416	-	-	-	-	-	19,416	133,671	153,087	67,575
Program Support	<u>107,560</u>	<u>2,426</u>	<u>62,943</u>	<u>18,840</u>	<u>583</u>	<u>4,765</u>	<u>197,117</u>	<u>253,672</u>	<u>450,789</u>	<u>420,946</u>
TOTAL	\$ <u>1,112,385</u>	\$ <u>3,867</u>	\$ <u>1,669,674</u>	\$ <u>1,803,668</u>	\$ <u>53,769</u>	\$ <u>267,294</u>	\$ <u>4,910,657</u>	\$ <u>561,935</u>	\$ <u>5,472,592</u>	\$ <u>6,549,076</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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